

CORRELATION BETWEEN PUNCTUALITY AND SELF ACTUALIZATION AMONG B.ED. STUDENTS

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Abstract: -

The aim of this research paper was to determine the correlation between Punctuality and Self Actualization of B.Ed. students. Punctuality is said to be the soul of business and there can be nothing more fundamental to the student's life than punctuality. Self Actualization reflects the intrinsic belief in the self .i.e. the overall opinion and value of a person .Description survey method was adopted in this study. This study revealed that the B.Ed. students are having a high level of Punctuality and self actualization. Overall, the study concludes that, there is a significant correlation between Punctuality and self actualization.

Introduction: -

The world is becoming very competitive. Quality of performance has become the key factor for personal progress. Parents want their child to climb the ladder of performance to as high as possible. Some students seem naturally enthusiastic about learning but many expect their instructors to inspire challenge and stimulate them .Both psychological and physical nature of human activity is generated by various motives, incentives and drives. The motivation interest and attitude, punctuality and self actualization are important factors affecting student's academic performance.

The present study attempts to examine the level of punctuality among B.Ed. college students and its correlation with self actualization. Punctuality and Self Actualization among students are the important issues that draw the attention of many researchers as good punctuality is essential to success at college level. Punctuality plays a vital role in improving student's academic performance .Each

and every student should have Punctuality ability which includes setting goals and priorities using time management mechanism and being organized in using time.

In this 21st century the competitive world, all the human beings required to develop new and varied skills. Our extremely important human characteristics affected by social interaction and physical activity are self actualization. In order to adopt and learn to new skills each student must have high level of self actualization in this competitive world. Student's punctuality, emotions are important because their thoughts and moods affect their subsequent motivational behavior and learning. It is terribly unfortunate that students who are bright and competent but lacking in self actualization will often shelf themselves and withdraws from programs of academic or vocational success, prematurely. Therefore the investigators have tried to focus on the kind of punctuality and self actualization among B.Ed. students.

Punctuality: - Punctuality could be seen in two dimensions that is coming to school, college or even in commercial office and closing at the right time. This attitude of punctuality is both the business of the teachers and students. Students Punctuality avail them the opportunity to attend all college programs and activities. Moreover, teachers may play an important role for improving punctuality issues among students. It is believed that if teachers do not manage time properly during the process of teaching in the classroom, it may interfere with the students learning.

Therefore time management and punctuality among teachers in teaching and learning process is also necessary to improve student's time management and punctuality issues. As today's B.Ed. College students are nation building teachers in future so it is very important to check awareness regarding Punctuality among B.Ed. college students.

Self Actualization: -

In 1943, psychologist Abraham Maslow introduced a theory describing human motivation in terms of satisfying categories of higher and lower needs. Since then this theory of a "Hierarchy of Needs" has gained greater popularity. According to Maslow, humankind's most primal and basic needs reside at the bottom of the pyramid: food, water, sleep, breathing, homeostasis, bodily functions and sexual needs. Above these are needs for safety, love and esteem correspondingly. At the tip

of the pyramid is the need that Maslow believes many people will never achieve self actualization.

According to Samuel Sackett (1988) many people fail to achieve self actualization because they lack trust in themselves, their environment and in others which prevents them from freely experiencing life. However, he believes that Self Actualization is possible despite the difficult process. Sackett also discusses the eight ways of knowing that Self Actualization has been achieved, as follows-

1. Knowing the ability to be fully absorbed and concentrated in ones efforts.
2. Knowing assesses fear versus growth, which states that choosing options that allow for growth within a person's career will lead them on the path towards Self Actualization.
3. Selflessness is the third way of knowing that one is Self Actualized, meaning that the individual must shut out the external world and become in touch with true feelings.
4. Dissatisfaction with compensation.
5. The ability to trust your own decisions and not be influenced by others.
6. A Self Actualized individual must be honest in his or her actions.
7. The recognition of peak experiences or experiences that seem to be of increased significance.
8. Openness to experience is the eighth and final way of knowing that one is self actualized.

Statement of the Problem:

The present problem is stated as “Correlation between Punctuality and Self Actualization among B.Ed. students.”

Objectives: -

To find out the correlation between Punctuality and Self Actualization of B.Ed. college students.

Hypotheses: -

1. There is no significant correlation between Punctuality and Self Actualization of Male B.Ed. college students.
2. There is no significant correlation between Punctuality and Self Actualization of Female B.Ed. college students

3. There is no significant correlation between Punctuality and Self Actualization of all B.Ed. college students.

Methodology: -

Looking at the nature of the study and variables, descriptive survey method was adopted in this study.

Sample: -

A total sample of 60 B.Ed. college students was drawn from Jalgaon district of Maharashtra state. All these B.Ed. colleges of Jalgaon district are affiliated to North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon. The sample was selected by using simple random technique. The sample consists of 33 Female and 27 Male students. The sample forms a representative sample of entire population.

Tools used:-

1. Punctuality Scale: -

Developed and standardized by Q.G.Alam and Ramji Srivastava (Azamgarh). This tool contains 60 statements on a five – point scale.

2. Self Actualization Inventory: -

Developed and standardized by K.N.Sharma (Jaipur). This tool contains 75 statements on a three – point scale. This tool is suitable for measures of Self Actualization.

Both tools are standardized and having reliability and validity.

Statistical Technique Used: -

For analysis of the obtained data quantitative techniques like coefficient of correlation was used.

Analysis of variables: -

Table 1: Coefficients of Correlation between Punctuality and Self Actualization of Male B.Ed. college students.

Null Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant correlation between Punctuality and Self Actualization of Male B.Ed. college students.

Variables	N (Male)	Calculated 'r' value	df	Table 'r' value	Comparison between Calculated 'r' value & Table 'r' value	Significance at 0.05 level	Null Hypothesis
Punctuality & Self Actualization	27	+0.621	25	+0.396	Calculated 'r' value > Table 'r' Value	Significant	Rejected

Table 1 show that, the Correlation between variables Punctuality and Self Actualization of Male B.Ed. college students is positive and significant at 0.05 levels of significance. So null hypothesis "There is no significant correlation between Punctuality and Self Actualization of Male B.Ed. college students." is rejected.

Table 2: Coefficients of Correlation between Punctuality and Self Actualization of Female B.Ed. college students.

Null Hypothesis 2: There is no significant correlation between Punctuality and Self Actualization of Female B.Ed. college students.

Variables	N (Female)	Calculated 'r' value	df	Table 'r' value	Comparison between Calculated 'r' value & Table 'r' value	Significance at 0.05 level	Null Hypothesis
Punctuality & Self Actualization	33	+0.715	31	+0.333	Calculated 'r' value > Table 'r' Value	Significant	Rejected

Table 2 show that, the Correlation between variables Punctuality and Self Actualization of Female B.Ed. college students is positive and significant at 0.05 levels of significance. So null hypothesis “There is no significant correlation between Punctuality and Self Actualization of female B.Ed. college students.” is rejected.

Table 3: Coefficients of Correlation between Punctuality and Self Actualization of all B.Ed. college students.

Null Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant correlation between Punctuality and Self Actualization of all B.Ed. college students.

Variables	N (All)	Calculated 'r' value	df	Table 'r' value	Comparison between Calculated 'r' value & Table 'r' value	Significance at 0.05 level	Null Hypothesis
Punctuality & Self Actualization	60	+0.746	58	+0.254	Calculated 'r' value > Table 'r' Value	Significant	Rejected

Table 3 shows that, the Correlation between variables Punctuality and Self Actualization of all B.Ed. college students is positive and significant at 0.05 levels of significance. So null hypothesis “There is no significant correlation between Punctuality and Self Actualization of all B.Ed. college students.” is rejected.

Major findings of the study: -

1. There is a highly significant and positive correlation between Punctuality and Self Actualization among Male B.Ed. college students.

2. There is a highly significant and positive correlation between Punctuality and Self Actualization among Female B.Ed. college students.
3. There is a highly significant and positive correlation between Punctuality and Self Actualization among all B.Ed. college students.

Conclusion: -

The present investigations have given strength and focus to the fact that Punctuality of B.Ed. College students have a positive significant correlation with Self Actualization. As today's B.Ed. College students are being pioneers i.e. teachers in future and they are having responsibility of developing whole student's life. Therefore all the educational institutions and society should approach the students in a positive way and give positive reinforcement. Parents, teachers and peers encouragement is correlated to self Actualization and positive self actualization is correlated to Punctuality.

Educational Implications: -

1. Understanding each individual as a unique personality is important.
2. Each individual has a certain amount of aggression, humor, virtue, happiness and poise .such combination of qualities defines and distinguishes one individual from the other and thus each individual becomes unique. so each individual has a different level of self individual and Punctuality.
3. Implementing psychological education course.
4. Arranging counseling classes.
5. Providing better home (hostel), health, school adjustment.
6. Competition and cooperation.
7. Rewards and Punishments.

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